

Research

Analysis of Higher Education in China: Some Characteristics and Development Strategies

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Abstract: Higher education in China as in many countries is a mixture of professional education and vocational education. It is an extension of secondary education. Since the reform and opening up, China's higher education has developed rapidly under the background of rejuvenating the country with talents. More and more colleges and universities are springing up every year, improving China's talent education system. Higher education has distinctive characteristics and can supplement and improve the shortcomings of traditional education. However, its development time is short and there are still some educational difficulties. In view of this, this article, based on the characteristics of higher education, analyzes the problems existing in higher education in China at this stage and provides solutions for reference. The Methods used here are mostly papers review and observation. Through these, we discovered that, although higher education in China is among the bests in the world, it still has a long way to go; especially if it aims to satisfy the UNESCO's goals on education.

Keywords: Keywords: higher education; characteristics; problems; countermeasures

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Introduction

Chinese higher education is changing at the pace of economic development over the past twenty years. From a necessary way, it tends towards democratization so that access to higher education is gradually becoming a right instead of being a privilege. Today we consider that reducing social gaps in education (under the heading of equity and social justice) is a new way of thinking which determines the current development of education around the world.

For a long time, higher education in China was part of the planned economy. The education system was based on state higher education establishments where everything was planned: budget, staff, allocation of jobs to most graduates, etc. This type of uniform educational institution actually proves ineffective in accommodating a larger number of students, and even if the State attaches great importance to this issue, higher education is then far from being able to meet the needs of the rapid development of the market economy and aspirations for personal training. So how to achieve the

development goal of higher education? China has no choice but to carry out a series of large-scale reforms in the field of higher education.

I. Characteristics of higher education in China

Higher education in China is characterized by many factors. Some of those factors which are: Career orientation, practicality of teaching, openness of running schools, Professional flexibility, and the decentralization of services at regional levels particularly draw our attention.

1. Career orientation

Higher education aims to improve students' technical level, transform theoretical knowledge into skill practice, arrange teaching plans based on the needs of social and professional positions, and determine the goal of cultivating talents. The talents cultivated by higher education are not comprehensive talents, but targeted talents. Technical talents cultivated by a certain occupational characteristic can only be qualified for a certain specific job. Occupational orientation is an important feature of higher education, which helps students plan their future work path during their study stage and continuously deepen a certain skill. The mastery of knowledge and the increasing experience in specific occupations enable students to accurately find their career positioning in the society.

2. Practicality of teaching

Higher education emphasizes the study of theoretical knowledge and requires students to master certain professional and cultural knowledge. Although some majors also have experiments and internships, they are only to prepare students for a better understanding of theoretical knowledge. Higher education mainly cultivates social technical talents, who are on the front line of production. Students are required to have certain operational abilities and cannot stay in theoretical culture. They should transform theory into practical operational abilities and put practical teaching as the top priority. This important position enables students to obtain not only academic certificates but also vocational qualification certificates. Higher education has strict requirements for teachers. Teachers must not only possess substantial theoretical and teaching knowledge, but also possess high theoretical operational skills. Therefore, teaching is required to be practical and promote students' hands-on ability. Prepare to adapt to job requirements better and faster in the future.

3. Openness of running schools

Higher education is open to all students and all professions in society, and establishes the concept of lifelong education. Higher education not only attaches importance to on-campus training, but also pays attention to off-campus and foreign practical training. The employing department and the school jointly cultivate and realize school-enterprise cooperation, so that students can join enterprises to work as soon as they graduate. They also strengthen cooperation and exchanges at both national and internal levels, so that students can actively go abroad, learn advanced foreign technologies, and improve their own skills, expand the scale of education and improve the level of school running.

4. Professional flexibility

Taking the example of Hebei Province; Students in higher education in Hebei Province mainly serve the local economy of Hebei Province, relying on the economic and educational resources of the Province and adjusting corresponding professional skills according to the adjustment of local industrial structure types. Higher education is highly career-specific and specializes in the positions and occupations required by society. Especially in a globalized society with

rapid economic development, new technologies, and the rapid development of emerging industries, colleges and universities are actively changing their curriculum structures, eliminating backward majors, and increasing emerging majors needed by the society.

5. Regionalization of services

The regional nature of service means that higher education is oriented to a certain region and serves the economic development of a certain region. Most colleges and universities are co-organized with local enterprises to provide outstanding talents for the enterprises. Different regions have different industrial structure types and development levels, and colleges and universities can only adapt to local conditions and formulate teaching plans based on the economic development status of the region; adjust corresponding teaching strategies according to the changes in the economic situation in the region, and always pay attention to the changes in the economic and social development environment in the region, in order to form a coordinated development of education and economy and improve the adaptability of graduates.

II. Problems with higher education in China

1. Higher education is not highly recognized by society.

Many parents still have traditional thinking about education. They believe that theoretical and academic higher education is the proper education. The traditional old concept seriously denies the value of higher education in cultivating talents, and lacks a sense of identity in higher education. Some parents are opposed to their children applying to colleges and universities. They would rather repeat their studies than go to colleges and universities. Even if some students are admitted, some of them do not register. Due to the short history of the development of colleges and universities, people still lack the correct knowledge and understanding of colleges and universities. In addition, the lack of publicity and public opinion has caused a gap in people's ideological understanding.

2. Teachers in remote areas have low standards and do not have high requirements for students.

At present, "teachers' professional abilities and levels in colleges and universities have not yet adapted to the requirements of industrial upgrading and technological development, and cannot effectively support the cultivation of high-level technical skills talents." With the advent of IT age, the quantity and quality of teachers cannot adapt to the development of the new era. Teachers should change the traditional teaching model and should not blindly focus on teaching. Facing the new situation without changing the teaching method, makes it difficult for certain teachers to adapt. Teachers have sufficient theoretical knowledge, but lack full practical ability. At the same time, teachers themselves have weak awareness and do not pay attention to the improvement of their own skills. There are insufficient teachers, heavy teaching tasks, insufficient hardware facilities, and the quality of student training has declined. With the continuous improvement of academic qualifications, the academic requirements for teachers have gradually increased, making it impossible for many teachers with excellent skills to enjoy that work. Therefore, even though many teachers have very substantial theoretical knowledge, they cannot transform it into practical skills, resulting in students only learning theoretical knowledge but lacking practical skills.

3. The funding system is not perfect and the infrastructure is weak.

Especially in remote areas, the school infrastructure is weak, the teaching equipment is outdated and backward, and the school running conditions need to be improved. The school's floor space is tight, the number of library books is too few, the types of sports facilities are incomplete, teaching funds per student are seriously insufficient, and practical teaching facilities as well as practical training infrastructure are seriously lagging behind. Most funds are invested in

undergraduate colleges and public institutions, so private higher education institutions receive very little government funding. Enterprises are the biggest beneficiaries of higher education, but they do not realize that higher education is closely related to them and provide a very small proportion of technical education funds. In addition to student tuition fees, most of the funding comes from government expenditures, resulting in insufficient funds. The main reason is that the education funding investment mechanism in many Provinces is not yet complete, and the government and enterprises lack a strict investment system. High student training fees and equipment purchase fees have increased the financial burden on colleges and universities.

III. The development path of higher education in China

1. Change traditional concepts and increase employment opportunities for graduates

Increase the publicity of higher education in society and let people know more about the talents cultivated by higher education. Create a good development environment and ideological atmosphere for the development of higher education. Reduce or even eliminate people's discriminatory notions against higher education, and truly regard higher education as an integral and important part of the education industry in different provinces. The government should assume the responsibility of promoting the development of higher education. The government has focused educational development on the conditions and needs of higher education, established the goal of giving priority to the development of higher education. It is time for the government to concentrate also on practical knowledge in Chinese universities. It can be done through multiplication of internship opportunities for students.

2. Strengthen the construction of "dual-qualified" teams

Building a teaching team is the foundation for the development of higher education in China, so it must also be socialized and diversified. Establish a mature training system, encourage collaboration between teachers, improve the construction of teacher training bases, and build a teacher training system. It is not only necessary to pay attention to the training of teachers' theoretical knowledge, but it is even more important to strengthen the training of professional skills. Only when theoretical knowledge and professional knowledge are possessed at the same time, and theoretical and operational skills are mastered at the same time, can one be called a qualified university teacher. At the same time, the school must strengthen the assessment and evaluation of teachers appointed by the school. "Double-qualified" teachers must have both a teacher qualification certificate and a professional and technical qualification certificate. The rewarding of outstanding teachers and elimination of low-level teachers should be automatic to encourage university teachers to improve their theoretical knowledge and professional skills.

3. Build a higher education system with local characteristics

As a type of education, higher education is an integral part and has a unique development system. Mr. Pan Maoyuan once proposed that the establishment of a characteristic higher education system should not only promote the adaptability of college graduates to society, but also be in line with the general trend of higher education development around the world. The change in the concept of employment education is that vocational education should adapt to students' employment needs. Not only should they have practical skills, but students must also have sufficient basic knowledge and solid application skills. Vocational and technical schools should promptly adjust their professional positioning and training model based on social needs and feedback from graduates, and form a distinct training plan to meet the social acceptance of graduates who need practical experience.

Conclusion

In general, higher education, because of its unique educational characteristics, is not only an expansion of personal education, but also a need for national development. Developing higher education and cultivating higher talents are

important ways to enhance China's comprehensive strength. China's higher education lacks certain environmental construction and also has some problems. Only by solving these problems can the Government better promote the development of higher education.

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